

Clash of Caste-Hierarchy: The Varṇa-System in Pāli Canons

Mukesh Mehta

Research Fellow, Department of Pāli & Buddhist Studies, Banaras Hindu University, Vārāṇasī – 221005

E-mail: mehtabhu18@gmail.com

Abstract

During the Mahājanapada period, the Śramaṇa culture became parallel or more popular to the Brāhmin culture. Many ancient traditions or sects flourished under this culture, out of which Jaina and Buddhist traditions became very popular. The biggest feature of both these traditions was that, they challenged and rejected the predominated Varṇa-system of the Brāhmin culture. This feature is reflected more vocally and strongly in the ancient Buddhist tradition. Siddhārtha Gautama, founder of Buddhism, himself was also from the Kśatriya-Varṇa. He was the son of Suddhodana, king of the Sākya-clan of Kosala Mahājanapada. Gautama Buddha not only strongly opposed this well-established Varṇa-system but also tried to convey the message that the superiority of human beings is not decided by their birth but upon their action. This was an agitational and revolutionary thing in the contemporary social system that Kśatriyas were trying to occupy the place of Brāhmins.

It can be said that this refusal of the Varṇa-system was a new beginning from view-point of social justice and equality. Many men and women from lower caste also ordained in Buddha-Dhamma and lived un-biased and un-discriminatory life after being a part of Buddhist-Saṅgha. We can easily observe a struggle or fight to attain a social supremacy inside Pāli canonical literature. By studying Pāli Canons it seems that, instead of eliminating the discriminatory Varṇa-system, there was a fight to retain its hierarchy and occupy the highest position in this system. So this paper is an attempt to examine that the rejection of the Varṇa-system, we often encounter in Pāli canonical literature, was really a rejection or it was a fight of social-supremacy or caste-hierarchy.

Keywords: Caste, Varṇa, Pāli-Canon, Social-Supremacy etc.

Introduction

At the time of the post Vedic-period or Mahājanapada-period¹ the Varṇa-system and

casteism and other discriminative social-systems, like Āśrama-system², not only gained social

¹ The *Āṅguttara Nikāya* frequently mentions the sixteen Mahājanapadas (or countries), which existed in the time of the Buddha. They are– Aṅga, Magadha, Kāsi, Kosala, Vajji, Malla, Cetiya, Vaṅga, Kuru, Pañcāla, Maccha, Sūrasena, Assaka, Avanti, Gandhāra and Kamboja. The first fourteen are included in the Majjhimadesa, the two last being in Uttarāpatha. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 1126). London: John Murray.] — “... yo imesaṃ soḷasannaṃ mahājanapadānaṃ pahūtarattaratanānaṃ issariyādhipaccaṃ rajjaṃ kāreyya, seyyathidaṃ – aṅgānaṃ, magadhānaṃ, kāsīnaṃ, kosalānaṃ, vajjīnaṃ, mallānaṃ, cetīnaṃ, vaṅgānaṃ, kurūnaṃ, pañcālānaṃ, macchānaṃ,

sūrasenānaṃ, assakānaṃ, avantīnaṃ, gandhārānaṃ, kambojānaṃ ...” [*The Āṅguttara Nikāya – Tikaṇipāta*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1960). (p. 197). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

² Varṇa and Āśrama two institutions so characteristic of the Hindu social order that the tradition is itself sometimes described as *Varṇāśrama Dharma* or the way of life characterised by these two institutions. While Varṇas (Brāhmin, Kśatriya, Vaiśya & Śūdra) relates to a person’s life as a member of a social organisation, Āśrama relates the individual’s life as such, which is described as undergoing the following four stages: (1) celibate student (Brahmacarya), (2) householder (Gṛhastha), (3) hermit (Vānaprastha) and (4) renunciant (Sanyāsa), in that order.

fortitude, but also created a big gap between the upper and lower Varṇas. Due to which, the great social reformers and humanitarians of that time, like the Mahāvīra and the Buddha had to struggle relentlessly to get rid of these social discriminations. During the Mahājanapada-period, the Śramaṇa-culture³ became parallel or more popular to the Brāhmin-culture or Vedic-culture. The main reason for the popularity of the Śramaṇa culture was its relatively more flexible nature. The nature of Śramaṇa culture was participatory, equitable and easily practicable for the common people of the society. Its rituals were devoid of ostentation and discrimination. Many ancient traditions or sects flourished under this culture, out of which Jaina and Buddhist traditions became very popular. The biggest feature of both these traditions was that, they challenged and rejected the predominated Varṇa-system of the Brāhmin culture.

If we observe the setup or structure of the Jaina tradition in the perspective of Jaina-Tīrthaṃkaras⁴, we find that almost all Tīrthaṃkaras came from the Kśatriya-Varṇa. The last Tīrthaṃkara Mahāvīra Swāmī was also the son of a Kśatriya king. Mahāvīra's father Siddhārtha⁵ was the king of Vaiśālī (Vesālī)⁶. It seems that, there was a struggle to dismiss or refuse the pre-established Varṇa-system. This struggle is reflected more vocally and strongly in the ancient Buddhist tradition. Siddhārtha-Gautama, founder of the Buddha-Dhamma,

[Cush, D., Robinson, C. A., & York, M. (Eds.). (2008). *Encyclopedia of Hinduism*. (p. 48). Abingdon: Routledge.]

³ Samaṇa (Pāli) – a wanderer, recluse, religieuse – the Buddha is often mentioned and addressed by non-Buddhists as Samaṇa; thus Samaṇas often opposed to Brāhmanas. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 8, p. 141). London: Pāli Text Society.]

⁴ Jainism is believed to have come down from unknown antiquity through 24 teachers, called Tīrthaṃkaras (founders of the faith). Mahāvīra Swāmī was the 24th and the last Tīrthaṃkara. [Chanchreek, K.L., & Jain, M.K. (Eds.). (2005). *Encyclopedia of Jaina Religion*. (vol. 1, pp. 64-112). New Delhi: Shree Publishers & Distributors.]

⁵ Gautam Buddha's pre-ascetic name was also Siddhārtha.

⁶ According to the Kalpasūtra, Vaiśālī was one of the greatest towns of the Ganges basin of Mahājanapada-period. [Dundas, P. (2002). *The Jains*. (p. 25). London: Routledge.]; At present time this is a district in Bihar state.

himself was also from the Kśatriya-Varṇa. He was the son of Suddhodana, chief of the Sākyan-clan of Kosala Mahājanapada. Gautama Buddha not only strongly opposed this well-established Varṇa-system but also tried to convey the message that the superiority of human beings is not decided by their birth (*jāti*) but upon their deed or action (*kamma*)⁷. This was an agitational and revolutionary thing in the contemporary social system that Kśatriyas were trying to occupy the place of Brāhmins. This was a matter of rebellion with the then social system and organization.

It can be said that this refusal of the Varṇa-system was a new beginning from view-point of social justice and equality. And no doubt it was really a new beginning, in such a time when no Śūdras were allowed to study or teach, Sākya's barber Upāli not only entered the Buddhist-order (the Saṅgha) but also, he later became *Vinayadhar*⁸ and recited Vinaya in first Buddhist-council held in Rājagaha⁹ after Mahāparinibbāna of the Buddha¹⁰. Many other men and women from lower Varṇa also ordained in Buddha-Dhamma and lived un-biased and un-discriminatory life after being a part of Buddhist-

⁷ *The Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 467-68). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.

⁸ One who knows or masters the Vinaya by heart, an expert in the Vinaya. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 7, p. 81). London: Pāli Text Society.]

⁹ Was a city, the capital of ancient Magadha. Rājagaha was closely associated with the Buddha's work. During the first year after the Enlightenment, therefore, the Buddha went to Rājagaha from Gayā. Bimbisāra and his subjects gave the Buddha a great welcome, and the king entertained him and a large following of monks in the palace. Just before his death, the Buddha paid a last visit there. At that time, Ajātasattu was contemplating an attack on the Vajjians. After the Buddha's death, Rājagaha was chosen by the monks, with Mahā Kassapa at their head, as the meeting-place of the First Convocation. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 722). London: John Murray.]; Sāṃskṛta version of Rājagaha is Rājagṛha. At present time this city is known as Rājagīra and situated in the Nālandā district of Bihar state.

¹⁰ Atha kho āyasmā mahākassapo saṅghaṃ nāpesi – “suṇātu me, āvuso, saṅgho. yadī saṅghassa pattakallaṃ, ahaṃ upāliṃ vinayaṃ puccheyya”nti. [The *Vinaya Piṭaka Cullavagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1956). (p. 408). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]; [Vinaya Piṭaka. Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Trans.). (2016). (p. 542). Delhi: Gautama Book Center.]

Saṅgha. But beside of all these examples, we can also see a struggle or fight to attain the social-supremacy inside Pāli canonical literature¹¹. By studying Pāli Canons it seems that, instead of eliminating the discriminatory Varṇa-system, there was a fight to retain its hierarchy and occupy the highest position in this system. Thus, this study is mainly focused to the following problems–

- Has the Varṇa-system been rejected in Pāli canonical literature or has it been accepted in a different way?
- Has the Varṇa-system reflected as a conflict of social-supremacy in Pāli canonical literature?

Rejecting the Varṇa-System

How complex the Varṇa-system existed in the society during Buddha's period can be seen in the *Lohicca-Sutta* of Dīghanikāyapāli. Since Buddha and his followers were opposed to caste-superiority or inferiority, they often had to face deprecation from Brāhmins who considered themselves superior. Once several youth students of the Brāhmin Lohicca approached Mahākaccāna's¹² wilderness hut while collecting firewood. They walked and wandered all around the hut, making a dreadful racket and all kinds of jeers– “These shavelings, fake ascetics, riffraff, black spawn from the feet of our Kinsman, the Lord! They're honoured, respected, esteemed, revered, and venerated by those who pretend to inherit Vedic-culture”¹³. This discrimination and

high-lowliness prevalent in the society used to hurt the mind and heart of the Buddha a lot. That is why he wanted that this inhuman conduct from the society should be ended and there would be no feeling of malice in anyone's mind and heart. Therefore, through his teachings, he always spread mutual love, brotherhood and friendship among monastic people, householders and other persons of the society. For him, no human-being was inferior or superior on the basis of birth– “When they reach the ocean, all the great rivers that is, the Ganges, Yamunā, Aciravatī, Sarabhū, and Mahī lose their names and clans and are simply considered ‘the ocean’. In the same way, when they go forth from the lay life to homelessness, all four castes aristocrats, priests, merchants, and workers lose their former names and clans and are simply considered ‘Sākyan ascetics’.”¹⁴

There are many examples in the *Pāli-Suttapiṭaka* where the Buddha rejects the caste and class supremacy outrightly. In the *Vāseṭṭhasutta*, Buddha explains a *mānavaka*¹⁵ named Vaśiṣṭha (Vāseṭṭha) through a variety of examples that the race of man is determined by his karma not by his birth– “No one is Brāhmin by birth, one is non-Brāhmin by birth. (One) becomes Brāhmin by deeds, (one) becomes non-Brāhmin by deeds”¹⁶. In *Assalāyana-Sutta* Buddha explains to a Brāhmin named Assalāyana that a

Salāyatanavagga. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1959). (p. 108). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

¹⁴ ... yā kāci mahānadiyo, seyyathidaṃ – gaṅgā yamunā aciravatī sarabhū mahī, tā mahāsamuddaṃ patvā jahanti purimāni nāmagottāni, ‘mahāsamuddo’ tveva saṅkhaṃ gacchanti; evamevaṃ kho, pahārāda, cattārome vaṇṇā – khattiyā, brāhmaṇā, vessā, suddā, te tathāgatappavedite dhammavinaye agārasmā anagāriyaṃ pabbajitvā jahanti purimāni nāmagottāni, ‘samaṇā sakyaputtiyā’... [The *Anguttara Nikāya – Aṭṭhakanipāta*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1960). (p. 310). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

¹⁵ A youth, young man (student), esp. a young Brāhmin. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 6, p. 151). London: Pāli Text Society.]

¹⁶ “Na jaccā brāhmaṇo hoti, na jaccā hoti abrahmaṇo.

Kammunā brāhmaṇo hoti, kammunā hoti abrahmaṇo”.

[The *Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakam*. Sāmkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 467). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

¹¹ The entire teachings of the Buddha are compiled under these three texts: *Vinaya-Piṭaka*, *Sutta-Piṭaka* and *Abhidhamma-Piṭaka*. These three texts are collectively called *Tipiṭaka*. Tipiṭaka is considered as Pāli canonical literature or Pāli Canon.

¹² Mahākaccāna (Kaccāyana) – One of the most eminent disciples of the Buddha, considered chief among expounders in full of the brief saying of the Buddha (saṅkhittena bhāsitaṃ vitthāreṇa atthaṃ vibhajantānaṃ). He was born at Ujjeni in the family of the chaplain of King Caṇḍappajjota, and was called Kaccāna both because of his golden colour and because Kaccāna was the name of his gotta. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 468). London: John Murray.]

¹³ “Ime pana muṇḍakā samaṇakā ibbhā kaṇhā bandhupādāpaccā, imesaṃ bhāratakānaṃ sakkatā garukatā mānitā pūjitā apacitā”ti. [The *Samyutta Nikāya* –

person indulging in sins and immoral acts, irrespective of any caste, is equally guilty and will also punishable equally without considering their caste or Varṇa. Therefore, neither any Varṇa is superior nor any inferior. Superiority and inferiority are determined by human's action or Karma¹⁷. Two Brāhmin māṇavaka named Vaśiṣṭha and Bhāradvāja were living together with the monks in *Pubbārāma*¹⁸ of *Sāvatti*¹⁹ for the purpose of being ordained into the Buddha's Dhamma. One evening, when they approached to the Buddha, he asked them, "you both belong to the Brāhmin family and wish to come to the shelter of Dhamma abandoning your caste and clan. Do your relatives and other Brāhmins not prevent you from doing this? Don't they condemn you?" Then Vaśiṣṭha replied– "Sir, the Brāhmins say, 'only Brāhmins are the highest caste; other castes are inferior. Only Brāhmins are the lightest caste; other castes are dark. Only Brāhmins are purified, not others. Only Brāhmins are Brahmā's rightful sons, born of his mouth, born of Brahmā, created by Brahmā, heirs of Brahmā. You've both abandoned the best caste to join an inferior caste, namely these shavelings, fake ascetics, riffraff, black spawn, originated from the feet of Brahmā. This is not right, it's not proper!' That's how the Brāhmins insult us sir."²⁰

¹⁷ "Taṃ kiṃ maññasi, assalāyana, ... suddova nu kho pāṇātipātī adinnādāyī kāmesumicchācārī musāvādī piṣuṇavāco pharusavāco samphappalāpī abhijjhālu byāpannacitto micchādīṭṭhi kāyassa bhedaṃ paramaṃ maraṇā apāyaṃ duggatiṃ vinipātaṃ nirayaṃ upapajjeyya, no brāhmaṇo"ti? [The *Majjhima Nikāya* – *Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāmkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 405). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

¹⁸ A park outside the eastern gate of Sāvatti. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 236). London: John Murray.]

¹⁹ Sāvatti (Śrāvastī) was the capital town of Kosala and one of the six great Indian cities during the period of the Buddha. The Buddha passed the greater part of his monastic life in Sāvatti. His first visit there was at the invitation of Anāthapindika. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 1126). London: John Murray.]

²⁰ "Brāhmaṇā, bhante, evamaḥamsu- 'brāhmaṇova seṭṭho vaṇṇo, hīnā aññe vaṇṇā. Brāhmaṇova sukko vaṇṇo, kaṇhā aññe vaṇṇā. Brāhmaṇāva sujjhanti, no abrahmaṇā. Brāhmaṇāva brahmuno puttā orasā mukhato jātā brahmajā Brāhmaṇaimmitā brahmadāyādā. Te tumhe seṭṭhaṃ vaṇṇaṃ hitvā hīnamattha vaṇṇaṃ ajjhupagatā, yadidaṃ muṇḍake samaṇake ibbhe kaṇhe bandhupādāpacce. Tayidaṃ na

The Buddha then tells them through various examples that people's superiority is decided not on the basis of birth, but on the basis of their actions. Person from (Kṣatriya, Brāhmin, Vaiśya or Śūdra) any Varṇa is equally responsible for their sins and virtues. Then the Buddha explains the history of the origin of the four Varṇas and tries to show that the four Varṇas are the four branches of the same tree, their base is the same, there is neither inferiority nor superiority among them and since Karma is the base of the origin of Varṇa, human-beings should be considered inferior or superior from their deeds and not from birth. Thereafter, he tells them about the origin of Śramaṇa that out of these four Varṇas, the person who walks on the path of Saddhamma is the superior to all²¹. Finally, he recited and admired a *gāthā*²² spoken by the *Brahmā Sanatkumāra*²³ in this context.

However, Buddha mentions the Kṣatriya as superior to the four Varṇas, both worldly and practically because they carry their gotra along. However, while supporting this *gāthā*, Buddha also supports the superiority of the Kṣatriya among the four Varṇas worldly or practically. But he also added that ultimately, the person with accomplished knowledge and good moral conducts is the best– "The aristocrat (warrior/Kṣatriya) is best of those people, who take clan as the standard. But one accomplished in

sādhu, tayidaṃ nappatirūpaṃ, yaṃ tumhe seṭṭhaṃ vaṇṇaṃ hitvā hīnamattha vaṇṇaṃ ajjhupagatā yadidaṃ muṇḍake samaṇake ibbhe kaṇhe bandhupādāpacce'ti. Evaṃ kho no, bhante, brāhmaṇā akkosanti paribhāsanti attarūpāya paribhāsāya paripuṇṇāya, no aparipuṇṇāya"ti. [The *Dīghanikāya* – *Pāthika Vagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). (pp. 63-64). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

²¹ " ... Dhammo hi, vāsetṭha, seṭṭho janetasmiṃ diṭṭhe ceva dhamme abhisamparāyaṇa." [The *Dīghanikāya* – *Pāthika Vagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 76). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

²² A verse, stanza, line of poetry, usually referring to an Anuṭṭhubbaṃ or a Tuṭṭhubbaṃ, & called a catuppādā *gāthā*, a stanza (śloka) of four half lines; As a style of composition it is one of the nine Aṅgas or divisions of the Canon. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 3, p. 78). London: Pāli Text Society.]

²³ (Brahmā) Sanatkumāra was a follower of the Buddha. The Brahmās appear to have been in the habit of visiting the deva-worlds too. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 338). London: John Murray.]

knowledge and conduct is best of gods and humans”²⁴. That verse was well sung by Brahmā Sanatkumāra, not poorly sung; well spoken, not poorly spoken; beneficial, not harmful, and I agree with it.²⁵

Not only Buddha but his enlighten disciples and *Arhata*²⁶ Bhikkhus also rejected this arrogance of caste-superiority. They considered this ego as propaganda and pretense. It is also worth seeing here that most of these disciples were from the Brāhmin caste. In the Madhura-Sutta of the Majjhimanikāya the King *Avantiputta* and Buddha's *aggasāvaka*²⁷ Mahākaccāna converse about the caste-superiority. King Avantiputta admits the same fact which has been discussed above between Vaśiṣṭha and the Buddha about Brahmin's pride of their caste. Mahākaccāna tells the King— “great King, that is just a propaganda that, ‘only Brāhmins are the highest caste ...’”²⁸. Then Mahākaccāna explains to the King, in the same way as the Buddha explains to Vaśiṣṭha (above) in Aggaññasutta, about the equality of Varṇa, and said— “All four Varṇas are the same.”²⁹

²⁴ “Brahmunā pesā, vāsetṭha, sanañkumārena gāthā bhāsītā –

“Khattiyo setṭho janetasmim, ye gottapaṭisārino.

Vijjācaraṇasampanno, so setṭho devamānuse”ti.

[*The Dīghanikāya – Pāthika Vagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 76). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

²⁵ “Sā kho panesā, vāsetṭha, brahmunā sanañkumārena gāthā sugītā, no duggītā. Subhāsītā, no dubbhāsītā. atthasamhitā, no anattasamhitā. anumatā mayā. Ahampi, vāsetṭha, evaṃ vadāmi. [ibid.]

²⁶ The state or condition of an Arahanta is perfection in the Buddhist sense (i.e. Nibbāna), final & absolute emancipation. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 1, p. 76). London: Pāli Text Society.]

²⁷ Aggasāvako – Chief disciple. Every Buddha has two chief disciples; those of Sākyamuni's were Sāriputta and Moggallāna. Fem.- aggasāvikā – a chief female disciple. Each Buddha has two of these; Sākyamuni's were Khemā and Uppalavannā. [Childers, R. C. (1875). *A dictionary of the Pāli language*. (p. 17). London: Trübner & Co.]

²⁸ “Ghosoyeva kho eso, mahārāja, lokasmim – ‘brāhmaṇova setṭho vaṇṇo, hīno añño vaṇṇo; ...’” [*The Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 310). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

²⁹ “... cattāro vaṇṇā samasamā honti ...”. [ibid. 312.]

Clash of Caste-Hierarchy

As we all know the Varṇa-system is a product of Vedic-culture. And the two main traditions (Jainism and Buddhism) of Śramaṇa culture that came into existence in opposition to Vedic culture were extremely opposed to this system. And it is also seen how Varṇa-system, rituals and all Vedic hypocrisies have been condemned in the literature of these traditions. We have just seen above many examples from Pāli canonical literature rejecting this system. But on the basis of some instances available in Pāli canonical literature, some scholars point out that the Varṇa-system has accepted here too by changing its hierarchy rather than completely rejecting the system³⁰. The position of Brāhmins is topmost in Vedic Varṇa-system, while in Buddhist literature we observe that Kśatriyas are fighting to occupy this place. There are many instances in Pāli-Tiṭṭaka which clearly show this struggle. And probably such observation by those scholars may be based on some of the Suttas in which the Kśatriyas have been described by the Buddha as superior to the Brāhmins. Here Kśatriyas were placed on the top rung, then after Brāhmins and the rest of two Varṇas were kept as earlier.

In *Ambaṭṭha-Sutta*, Ambaṭṭha māṇavaka, full of arrogance of caste-ism and gotra-ism, goes to debate with the Buddha and behaves indiscriminately and rudely. Seeing this, Buddha asks him that if he behaves similar with his senior relatives and teachers, then Ambaṭṭha says— “No, Master Gotama. For it is proper for one Brāhmin to converse with another Brāhmin while both are walking, standing, sitting, or lying down. But as to these shavelings, fake ascetics, riffraff, black spawn originated from the feet of Brahmā, I converse with them as I do with Master Gotama”³¹. Ambaṭṭha was also hurt by the fact

³⁰ Kumar, B. (2016, September 22). “*Problem of caste system as available in Pāli texts*” [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/NbxHFOhTveI> (00:50:00 & 01:07:42).

³¹ “No hidaṃ, bho gotama. gacchanta vā hi, bho gotama, gacchantena brāhmaṇo brāhmaṇena saddhiṃ sallapitumarahati, ṭhito vā hi, bho gotama, ṭhiteṇa brāhmaṇo brāhmaṇena saddhiṃ sallapitumarahati, nisinna vā hi, bho gotama, nisinnena brāhmaṇo brāhmaṇena saddhiṃ sallapitumarahati, sayāno vā hi, bho gotama, sayānena

that the Sākyaans do not respect the Brāhmins and since Buddha was related to the Sākya- dynasty, he was showing such disrespect to him– “Master Gotama, there are these four castes– aristocrats, Brāhmins, merchants, and workers. Three of these castes, aristocrats, merchants, and workers, in fact succeed only in serving the Brāhmins. It is neither proper nor appropriate that the Sākyaans, ruffraff that they are, don’t honour, respect, revere, worship, or venerate Brāhmins”³². Then the Buddha narrates the history of the dynasty of Ambaṭṭha Brāhmin, which shows that Ambaṭṭha is a descendant of the slave of the Sākyaans. Thus the Sākyaans are superior and the *gotta*³³ which Ambaṭṭha belonged from is inferior. Here, Buddha also try to establish that Kśatriyas are superior to Brāhmins– “So Ambaṭṭha, either from women’s (mother) side or from men’s (father) side the Kśatriyas are superior and Brāhmins are inferior”³⁴.

Once *Pasenadi*³⁵ the king of *Kosala*³⁶ asks Buddha about similarity or difference among the

brāhmaṇo brāhmaṇena saddhiṃ sallapitumarahati. Ye ca kho te, bho gotama, muṇḍakā samaṇakā ibbhā kaṇhā bandhupādāpaccā, tehipi me saddhiṃ evaṃ kathāsallāpo hoti, yathariva bhotā gotamenā”ti. [*The Dīghanikāya – Sīlakkhandhavagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). (pp. 78-79). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

³² “Cattārome, bho gotama, vaṇṇā- khattiyā brāhmaṇā vessā suddā. imesaṇhi, bho gotama, catunnaṃ vaṇṇānaṃ tayo vaṇṇā – khattiyā ca vessā ca suddā ca – aññadatthu brāhmaṇasseva paricārakā sampajjanti. Tayidaṃ, bho gotama, nacchannaṃ, tayidaṃ nappatirūpaṃ, yadime sakyā ibbhā santā ibbhā samānā na brāhmaṇe sakkaronti, na brāhmaṇe garuṃ karonti, na brāhmaṇe mānenti, na brāhmaṇe pūjenti, na brāhmaṇe apacāyanti”ti. [ibid. 79.]

³³ [Vedic- gotra – to go] ancestry, lineage. There is no word in English for *gotta*. It includes all those descended, or supposed to be descended, from a common ancestor. A *gotta* name is always distinguished from the personal name, the name drawn from place of origin or residence, or from occupation, and lastly from the nick-name. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 3, p. 84). London: Pāli Text Society.]

³⁴ “Iti kho, ambaṭṭha, itthiyā vā itthiṃ karitvā purisena vā purisaṃ karitvā khattiyāva seṭṭhā, hīnā brāhmaṇā. [*The Dīghanikāya – Sīlakkhandhavagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 85). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

³⁵ King of Kosala and contemporary of the Buddha. He was the son of *Mahākosala*, and was educated at Takkaṣilā where, among his companions, were the Licchavi-Mahāli and the Malla prince Bandhula. On his return home his father was so pleased with his proficiency in the various arts that he forthwith made him king. [Malalasekera, G. P.

four Varnaas– “Sir, there are these four classes– aristocrats, priests, merchants, and workers. Is there any difference between them?” Buddha replied– “of the four classes, two are said to be preeminent– the aristocrats and the priests. That is, when it comes to bowing down, rising up, greeting with joined palms, and observing proper etiquette.”³⁷

Assalāyana Brāhmin asked the same question to the Buddha that the *Madhura*³⁸ King Avantiputta asked to the Mahākaccāna. Then the Buddha did a counter question to Assalāyana– “What do you think, Assalāyana? Have you heard that in Greece and Persia and other foreign lands there are only two classes, masters and bonded servants; and those masters may become servants, and servants masters?” Assalāyana replied in ‘yes’ to this question. Then the Buddha tells him that when the superiority and inferiority of a person in foreign countries is not caste-based, then what is the special ability in the Brāhmins here that they forcibly prove themselves to be the superior? It means the Buddha wanted to say that one could not be considered superior only by being born as a

(1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 168). London: John Murray.]

³⁶ A country inhabited by the Kosalā, to the north-west of Magadha and next to Kāśī, it is mentioned second in the list of sixteen Mahājanapadas. Ruled over by Pasenadi, who was succeeded by his son Viḍūḍabha. By this time Kāśī was under the subjection of Kosala, for we find that when Bimbisāra, king of Magadha, married Kosaladevī, daughter of Mahākosala and sister of Pasenadi, a village in Kāśī was given as part of the dowry. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1937). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 1, p. 695). London: John Murray.]

³⁷ “Cattārome, mahārāja, vaṇṇā – khattiyā, brāhmaṇā, vessā, suddā. Imesaṃ kho, mahārāja, catunnaṃ vaṇṇānaṃ dve vaṇṇā aggamakkhāyanti – khattiyā ca brāhmaṇā ca – yadidaṃ abhivādanapaccuṭṭhānāñjalikammaṣāmicikammān”ti. [*The Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāmkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (pp. 375-376). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

³⁸ or Madhurā – The capital of Surasena, situated on the Yamunā. Its king, soon after the death of Bimbisāra, was Avantiputta, who, judging by his name, was probably related to the royal family of Ujjeni. Madhurā was visited by the Buddha, but there is no record of his having stayed there. Later, about 300 B.C., Madhurā became a Jaina centre, but when Fa-Hsien and Hiouen-Thsang visited it, Buddhism was flourishing there, and there were many saṅghārāmas and stūpas. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2, p. 438). London: John Murray.]

Brāhmin and even a lower caste person can deserve to be the superior.

Similarly, once another Brāhmin named Esukāri also questions Buddha about the duties and wealth (or livelihood) prescribed for all Varṇas by Brāhmins— “Master Gotama, the Brāhmins prescribe four kinds of service— a priest, an aristocrat, a merchant, and a worker may all serve a priest. An aristocrat, a merchant, and a worker may all serve an aristocrat. A merchant or a worker may serve a merchant. Only a worker may serve a worker. These are the four kinds of service that the Brāhmins prescribe. What do you say about this”³⁹? “Master Gotama, the Brāhmins prescribe four kinds of wealth (livelihood). They prescribe *alms livelihood* for priests, *bow and quiver livelihood* for aristocrats, *farming and animal husbandry livelihood* for merchants, *scythe and flail livelihood* for workers. What do you say about this”⁴⁰? Rejecting this unfair and immoral system established by the Brāhmins, the Buddha says that— “I say that you should serve those if serving them makes you grow in faith, ethics, learning, generosity, and wisdom. I say that you shouldn’t serve those if serving them doesn’t make you grow in faith, ethics, learning⁴¹ and “I consider the ‘*Ārya Lokottara Dharma*’ (the path

shown by and the Dhamma preached by the Buddha)⁴² as the capital/wealth of human”.

Once there was a dispute between Vaśiṣṭha and Bhāradvāja māṇavaka on whether a person should be considered a Brāhmin on the basis of birth or on the basis of karma. Bhāradvāja's view was that one should be considered a Brāhmin on the basis of birth, while Vaśiṣṭha's opinion was the opposite. To settle their dispute, they go to the Buddha, and Vaśiṣṭha tells the Buddha— “We have a dispute regarding the question of ancestry. Bhāradvāja says that one is a Brāhmin due to birth, but I declare it's because of one's actions. Oh seer, know this as our debate”⁴³. The Buddha then told the Vaśiṣṭha and Bhāradvāja māṇavaka about the merit and qualities of a Brāhmin through 56 verses (most of these verses can also be found in the *Brāhmaṇa-vaggo* of *Dhammapada* whose second lines usually end with *...tamahaṃ brūmi brāhmaṇaṃ*⁴⁴) and said that only those persons who have these qualities can be considered as Brāhmins.

Another example can be seen in the *Mahāparinibbāna-sutta* and *Mahāsudassana-sutta* in which *Ānanda*⁴⁵ forbids Buddha to get *parinibbāna*⁴⁶ in a small and boonies place like

³⁹ “Brāhmaṇā, bho gotama, catasso pāricariyā paññapenti – ‘brāhmaṇo vā brāhmaṇaṃ paricareyya, khattiyo vā brāhmaṇaṃ paricareyya, vesso vā brāhmaṇaṃ paricareyya, suddo vā brāhmaṇaṃ paricareyyā’ti. ‘Khattiyo vā khattiyam paricareyya, vesso vā khattiyam paricareyya, suddo vā khattiyam paricareyyā’ti. ‘Vesso vā vessam paricareyya, suddo vā vessam paricareyyā’ti. ‘Suddova suddam paricareyya. idha bhavaṃ gotamo kimāhā’ti? [The *Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (pp. 443-44). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

⁴⁰ “Brāhmaṇā, bho gotama, cattāri dhanāni paññapenti – brāhmaṇā brāhmaṇassa sandhanaṃ paññapenti bhikkhācariyaṃ; brāhmaṇā khattiyassa sandhanaṃ paññapenti dhanukalāpaṃ; brāhmaṇā vessassa sandhanaṃ paññapenti kasigorakkhaṃ; brāhmaṇā suddassa sandhanaṃ paññapenti asitabyābhaṅgiṃ. Idha bhavaṃ gotamo kimāhā’ti? [ibid. p. 441.]

⁴¹ Yaṃ hissa, brāhmaṇa, paricarato pāricariyāhetu saddhā vaḍḍhati, sīlaṃ vaḍḍhati, sutam vaḍḍhati, cāgo vaḍḍhati, paññā vaḍḍhati, tamahaṃ ‘paricaritabba’nti. [ibid. p. 443.]

⁴² evameva kho ahaṃ, brāhmaṇa, ariyaṃ lokuttaraṃ dhammaṃ purisassa sandhanaṃ paññapemi. [ibid. p. 445.]

⁴³ “Jātiyā brāhmaṇo hoti, bhāradvājo iti bhāsati. Ahañca kammunā brūmi, evaṃ jānāhi cakkhuma. [The *Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 463). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

⁴⁴ *Dhammapada*. Dhammarakkhita, Bhikkhu. (Trans.). (2017). (pp. 124-132). Delhi: Motilāla Banārasīdāsa.

⁴⁵ One of the principal disciples of the Buddha. First cousin of the Buddha and was deeply attached to him. He came to earth from *Tusita* and was born on the same day as the Bodhisatta Gotama, his father being Amitodana the Sākya, brother of Suddhodana. Mahānāma and Anuruddha were therefore his brothers (or they were probably step-brothers). [Malalasekera, G. P. (1937). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 1, p. 249). London: John Murray.]

⁴⁶ Parinibbāna (or full-Nibbāna) is a synonym for Nibbāna; this term, therefore, does not refer exclusively to the extinction of the five groups of existence at the death of the Enlightened-One, though often applied to it [Thera, Ñyānātiloka. (1988). *Buddhist dictionary: Manual of Buddhist terms and doctrines*. (p. 239). Kandy: Buddhist Publication Society.]. And, the term Mahāparinibbāna is used for death of the Buddha or Enlightened-One.

*Kusīnarā*⁴⁷ – “Sir, please don’t become fully extinguished in this little hamlet, this jungle hamlet, this branch hamlet. There are other great cities such as Campā, Rājagaha, Sāvattihī, Sāketa, Kosambī, and Benares. Let the Buddha become fully extinguished there. There are many well-to-do aristocrats, priests, and householders there who are devoted to the Buddha. They will perform the rites of venerating the Realized One’s corpse”⁴⁸. In *Meṇḍakapañho* section of the text *Milindapañho*, there is an interesting dialogue between Bhikkhu Nāgasena and King Milinda about the Buddha being a Brāhmin or a Kśatriya. King Milinda asks Bhante Nāgasena that what is the reason that Buddha calls himself Brāhmin and Kśatriya both? Then Nāgasena explains King Milinda that Buddha is called Brāhmin and Kśatriya both on the basis of his deeds not on the basis of his birth⁴⁹.

On the basis of the above instances of Pāli canonical literature, scholars conclude that the emphasis of Buddha and his disciples like Ānanda (who belonged to Śākya-Kśatriya clan) was not on the abolition of Varṇa-system. Rather, they wanted to place the Kśatriyas at the top of this system by changing the hierarchy of the pre-existing Varṇa-system. They consider it as a conflict of social-supremacy. But, while rendering

⁴⁷ The capital of the Mallas and the scene of the Buddha's death. At that time it was a small city, ‘a branch-township with wattle-and-daub houses in the midst of the jungle,’ and Ānanda was, at first, disappointed that the Buddha should have chosen it for his Parinibbāna. But the Buddha, by preaching the Mahā-Sudassana Sutta, pointed out to him that in ancient times it had been Kusāvati, the royal city of the King Maha-Sudassana. [Malalasekera, G. P. (1937). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 1, p. 653). London: John Murray.]

⁴⁸ “Mā, bhante, bhagavā imasmim khuddakanagarake ujjāṅgalanagarake sākhanagarake parinibbāyi. Santi, bhante, aññāni mahānagarāni. Seyyathidaṃ – campā, rājagahaṃ, sāvattihī, sāketaṃ, kosambī, bārāṇasī; ettha bhagavā parinibbāyatu. Ettha bahū khattiyamahāsālā brāhmaṇamahāsālā gahapatimahāsālā tathāgate abhippasannā, te tathāgatassa sarīrapūjaṃ karissanti”ti. [*The Dīghanikāya – Mahāvagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). (p. 130). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.]

⁴⁹ 1. *The Milindapañho*: Being dialogues between King Milinda and the Buddhist sage Nāgasena. Trenckner, V. (Ed.). (1880). (p. 225). London: Williams and Norgate. 2. Davids, T. W. (Trans.). (1894). (p. 25). *The questions of King Milinda*. London: Oxford.

this type of opinion, scholars often ignore the fact that Buddha was a spiritual person, not a ruler of any kingdom. Outside the Saṅgha, there was always a society in which order of the King was prevalent and also a strong pre-established social-system was present there. Therefore, the Buddha could not suddenly deny the prevailing Varṇa-system on which the whole society was functioning and which was the foundation of the contemporary society. But yes, he could certainly fight against social inequality and discrimination, that he was doing through his Dhamma and the Saṅgha.

If we observe and analyse those instances carefully, we get to know that the Buddha or his disciples did not intend to change the hierarchy of Varṇa-system. As far as the Ambaṭṭha Sutta is concerned, on the basis of which the such objection is imposed on the Buddha, we clearly see that the Buddha questions the Brāhmins who belonged to the *gotta* of Ambaṭṭha (i.e. kaṇhāyana gotta) only not the entire Brāhmin community. And the Buddha did this because Ambaṭṭha was extremely proud of his caste-gotra and he was filled with hatred for people of other castes. It was a type of *micchā-ditṭhi*⁵⁰ that needed to be redressed and Buddha did the same. In the entire philosophy of Buddha, *kamma* (action) is predominant; he considers *kamma* as the yardstick of human’s ability and tries to establish equality in the society.

It can be said that if the Buddha did not reject the Varṇa-system completely, then he did not even accept this system. He continued to fight this discriminatory system by following *middle-path* over the life. This is the reason why we find examples like *Kaṅkkhala Sutta* and *Ambaṭṭha Sutta* where his view on the Varṇa-system is often criticized. But in spite of all these things, two questions are absolutely relevant– first, why only Brāhmin and Kśatriya were glorified in the entire Pāli-Canon and second, wherever the four Varṇas have been discussed in the Pāli-Canon, why

⁵⁰ Wrong-views; one who holds wrong views. [Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 6, p. 156). London: Pāli Text Society.]

always Kśatriyas have been kept at the first place and the Brāhmin on the second (*khattiyo–brāhmaṇo–vesso–suddo*)?

Conclusion

On analysing the Varṇa-system as described in Pāli Canons, some very important and interesting things related to the ancient Indian social-structure are revealed. Brāhmins (priests) and Kśatriyas (aristocrats) always seem to be struggling to stay at the top of the caste-hierarchy. The Vaiśyas (merchants), which were financially strong, were

providing all possible financial aid to the Saṅgha, by influencing the Buddha-Dhamma. Due to which a new anti-Brāhminical religion or tradition (i.e. Buddhism) was growing very fast. Śūdras (workers) were always being targeted by Brāhmins and sometimes by Kśatriyas and Vaiśyas also. But with the help and support of Buddha-Dhamma and Saṅgha, Śūdras were constantly struggling to improve their position. Therefore, a kind of caste-struggle can often be seen in Pāli Canons and this struggle exists even at the present time in Indian society.

References

Primary Sources :

- Dhammapada*. Dhammarakkhita, Bhikkhu. (Trans.). (2017). Delhi: Motilāla Banārasīdāsa.
- The Aṅguttara Nikāya – Aṭṭhakanipāta*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1960). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Aṅguttara Nikāya – Tikanipāta*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1960). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Dīghanikāya – Mahāvagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Dīghanikāya – Pāthika Vagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Dīghanikāya – Sīlakkhandhavagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1958). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Majjhima Nikāya – Majjhima Paṇṇāsakaṃ*. Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Ed.). (1958). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Milindapañho: Being dialogues between King Milinda and the Buddhist sage Nāgasena*. Trenckner, V. (Ed.). (1880). London: Williams and Norgate.
- The Saṃyutta Nikāya – Saḷāyatanavagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1959). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.
- The Vinaya Piṭaka Cullavagga*. Kaśyapa, B.J. (Ed.). (1956). Nālandā: Nava Nālandā Mahāvihāra.

Secondary Sources :

- Chanchreek, K.L., & Jain, M.K. (Eds.). (2005). *Encyclopedia of Jaina Religion*. New Delhi: Shree Publishers & Distributors.
- Childers, R. C. (1875). *A dictionary of the Pāli language*. London: Trübner & Co.
- Cush, D., Robinson, C. A., & York, M. (Eds.). (2008). *Encyclopedia of Hinduism*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- Davids, R., & Stede, W. (Eds.). (1952). *The Pāli text society's Pāli-English dictionary*. (Vol. 1-8). London: Pāli Text Society.
- Davids, T. W. Rhys. (Trans.). (1894). *The questions of King Milinda*. London: Oxford.
- Dundas, P. (2002). *The Jains*. London: Routledge.
- Kumar, B. (2016, September 22). "Problem of caste system as available in Pāli texts" [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/NbxHFOhTveI>.
- Malalasekera, G. P. (1937). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 1). London: John Murray.
- Malalasekera, G. P. (1938). *Dictionary of Pāli proper names*. (Vol. 2). London: John Murray.
- Sāṃkṛtyāyana, R. (Trans.). (2016). *Vinaya Piṭaka*. Delhi: Gautama Book Center.
- Thera, Ñānātiloka. (1988). *Buddhist dictionary: Manual of Buddhist terms and doctrines*. Kandy: Buddhist Publication Society.